

DEVELOPMENT OF THERMOPLASTIC INTERLEAF FILMS WHICH BUILD UP A CONTROLLED MORPHOLOGY FOR TOUGHENING OF RTM RESINS

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SUMMARY

The present paper aims to develop a novel technique to obtain tough thermoset systems for RTM processing. The novel technique is based on the use of tailored thermoplastic interleaves that, upon heating, build up a controlled morphology in the interlaminar region.

Keywords: interleaf, toughening, resin transfer molding, thermoset, thermoplastic

INTRODUCTION

The main requirement for a resin to be injected in a dry preform is the have low viscosity in the order of 1Pa.s [1]. The addition of thermoplastic tougheners is the most accepted toughening strategy in aerospace applications to overcome the brittleness of thermoset [2]. However, thermoplastic cause an increase of several order of magnitude of the viscosity for the blends.

Some solutions have been proposed in the literature based on the use of hyperbranched modifiers [3] or soluble fibers [4]. The first approach can lead to decrement of the thermal properties of the blends [5] especially when aromatic ammine are used as curing agents. The adoption of soluble thermoplastic fibers is viable option to obtain high performance thermoset systems for aerospace applications. However, these developments are related to the use of proprietary thermoplastic systems.

In order to overcome the traditional toughening strategy used for pre-preg a novel approach based on the use of unmodified thermoset systems together with thermoplastic interleaf films which build up a controlled morphology is proposed.

Experimental

The thermoplastic interleafs have been obtained from aromatic polymers normally used as tougheners for epoxies. The polymers used were all from commercial sources. Both press melting and solvent casting have been used to manufacture interleafs. The use of different film manufacturing techniques was needed in order to control the thickness of the film. The tougheners used for the present study were obtained from commercial sources and used without further purification. The tradename and producer of each polymeric toughener is reported in table 1.

Table 1 Commercial toughener used for the present study

Tradename	Producer	Chemical Name
Radel A100	Solvay	Polyethersulfone
Ultem 1000	Sabic	Polyetherimide
PES 5003P	Sumitomo	Polyethersulfone

The thermoplastic interleaf were melt processed in a Carver press. The melting temperature used are reported in table 2 together with the average thickness obtained (a pressure of 50bar was used for all polymers).

Table 2 Processing conditions and Thickness for melt processed films

Polymer	Melt Temperature [°C]	Average Thickness [µm]
Radel A100	280	180
Ultem 1000	350	200
PES 5003P	320	190

The solvent casting technique was used in order to obtain thin films. The polyethersulphone polymers were dissolved in dichloromethane while the Ultem 1000 in chloroform. The average thickness for the melt processed films was 20-30µm. The control of the thickness was achieved varying the solution concentration.

Two epoxy resins were used: the di-functional DGEBF; the tri-functional TGAP. Aromatic curing agents were used as hardner (ie. MDEA and DDS) (Figure 1). The epoxy resins were obtained by Vantico. The hardners were purchased by Aldrich.

Figure 1 Epoxies and amines used in the study

Different techniques (hot stage microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and rheology) were used to assess the behavior of the thermoplastic interleaf embedded in the epoxy resin.

Results

To evaluate on a first level the behavior of the thermoplastic interleaf film if wetted by hot resin the interleaf embedded in resin were studied under the hot stage microscopy. The hot stage microscopy experiment for Radel A100 (Figure 2) lead to the conclusion that thin ($20\mu\text{m}$) thermoplastic interleaf can dissolve in the resin and create a gradient or continuous morphology depending on several parameters. When thick interleaf films ($180\mu\text{m}$) was used the dissolution was not complete (Figure 3). Similar results were obtained when different resins or interleafs were used.

Figure 2 Hot stage experiments at 170°C with TGAP/MDEA resin when thin interleaf of Radel A100 was used.

Figure 2 Hot stage experiments at 170°C with TGAP/MDEA resin when thick interleaf of Radel A100 was used.

The results obtained by the hot stage analysis seems to sustain the finding that thin films can be dissolved in the resin while the thick films cannot. An explanation of this observation can be given considering a simple calculation if one refer to Figure 3. In the figure a simple mode of a film of thickness Th_f is embedded between two resin films with a total thickness of Th_R . If this consider this model and the relative density of the resin and of the thermoplastic can easily calculate the relative amount of toughener compared to the resin. If one suppose the resin thickness Th_R to be 150 μm and the resin film to be 20 μm thick the relative amount of toughner is about 16% wt. If a film with 50 μm is considered the relative amount of thermoplastic about 41% wt . The latter percentage is far too high to allow the thermoplastic to dissolve in the resin even if standard melt procedure starting from thermoplastic powder are used.

Figure 3 Simplified model

The use of the hot stage microscopy technique is useful in order to evaluate the dissolution behavior of the interleaf films. However, this test can be altered by many factors such as the presence of excessive bubbling, the contact between the interleaf and the glass slide which contains the resin and the interleaf etc. In order to overcome the limitations of this approach we attempted to study the dissolution behavior of the thermoplastic interleaf with the parallel plate rheometry. The complex viscosity is particularly sensitive to variation of the phase behavior of epoxy/thermoplastic systems as shown for phase separating systems in the literature [6]. Different samples prepared mixing epoxy resin and chopped interleaf were analyzed within the parallel plate rheometry. Figure 4 shows the viscosity trace for a typical sample were the resin

containing chopped interleaf is compared to a resin system produce by melt mixing of thermoplastic powder with the resin. The latter procedure is the standard technique used to prepare resin system for melt impregnation of dry fabric in the production of preps.

Figure 4 Rheology comparison of resin systems containing chopped interleaf vs epoxy system prepared with standard melt mixing procedure.

The figure clearly shows that the viscosity of the chopped system is higher in the first stage compared to the powder systems. The dissolution of the interleaf which occurs during the heating of the resin lead to the lowering of the viscosity which tends to coincide with the standard system. After curing the two samples were analyzed under TEM. Figure 5 shows the results.

Figure 5 TEM images: right interleaf system; left powder system

The TEM analyses confirm that both systems show similar phase separation morphology. A small difference is observed between the two systems which can be interpreted as a consequence of the different induction time which characterize the chopped systems to obtain the fully dissolved systems.

Conclusions

The present paper was focused on the study of a novel technique to obtain RTM toughened systems. The technique is based on the use of thermoplastic interleaf which dissolve upon heating of the resin. The hot stage technique proved that the thick films cannot dissolve easily. The thin films were proved to dissolve leading to systems with morphology and mechanical properties which are similar to the system prepared via the melt mixing route which is used for pre preg systems.

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